

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

**Report on development and delivery of training on Argo floats
for the National Antarctic Scientific Center**

Deliverable D10.1

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Cover sheet: Floats by Olena Marushevskaya.

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1. Publishable summary

This deliverable covers the training sessions on the Argo floats deployment. The training was held by OCEAN:ICE partners for the staff members of the National Antarctic Scientific Center who are going to deploy these floats in Antarctica in the next months. By addressing observational gaps in the Southern Ocean, the data collected by NASC with the floats will improve the accuracy of models used to predict ice melt, ocean circulation, and long-term climate impacts. More specifically, the data will be critical in filling in existing observational gaps and enhancing the precision of climate models. The improved data will contribute to more accurate predictions of Antarctic ice melt and its global impacts.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the training features and contents

Scope of the training

The scope of this training was two-fold:

- Bring everyone up to speed on the oceanography of the region and together plan how we may deploy the floats and analyst later the data. This zone has a seasonal evolution we are trying to understand on the Bransfield Strait ocean front and this has an impact on the weather in the region and this is where also the NASC long term observation at Vernasky station are also very interesting for OCEAN:ICE WP3 and WP11.
- Deliver knowledge of Pierre Dutrieux and Markus Janout have in the use of the autonomous Argo floats produced by NKE instrumentation (e.g., ARVOR 1), which were purchased by the NASC in 2024 for the operating the equipment to the benefit of the OCEAN: ICE project, and assist you in deploying, receiving data and analyzing the data of these floats.

Dates of the trainings:

A first training session was held on 22 August 2024. The second training session was held on 30 September 2024.

Trainers:

- British Antarctic Survey (BAS): Dr. Andrew Meijers, Dr. Pierre Dutrieux, who have been working on the Noosphera ship in the past and have been working with the Argo floats produced by NKE extensively in the past.
- University of Delaware (collaborating with OCEAN:ICE): Dr. Carlos Moffat. Expert in the dynamics in the region of the upcoming cruises.
- Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research: Dr. Markus Janout, who is an expert also in the regions and equipment covered by the upcoming cruises.

Participants of the National Antarctic Scientific Center (NASC): Dr. Viktor Komorin, Sofiia Zhrebchuk, Oleksandr Lepeshkin, Yurii Oleinik, Yurii Dykhanov, Oleksandr Poluden.

Topics covered during the training sessions

The training sessions have covered the items listed below.

Overview of Marine Float Technologies: BAS presented a comprehensive overview of marine floats designed for oceanographic data collection in the Southern Ocean, of their set up, components and functionalities. These floats are vital for gathering data on key environmental parameters and are integral to OCEAN:ICE's goal of expanding data coverage in remote and under-monitored regions.

Technical Specifications: The marine floats are equipped with advanced sensors to measure critical oceanographic variables such as salinity, temperature, chemical composition, pressure. The floats are designed to withstand harsh Southern Ocean conditions, including sub-zero temperatures and high salinity levels, ensuring they can function reliably in extreme environments. The representative noted that the floats have been tailored to operate efficiently in areas with varying depths and ice cover, making them suitable for the OCEAN: ICE project.

Float Deployment Process: The procedures for deploying the floats have been thoroughly analyzed during the training. It has been emphasized how they are strategically placed in the Southern Ocean to capture data from regions lacking observational coverage. Deployment sites have been selected based on gaps identified in the project's existing data sets, particularly where ocean circulation and sea ice processes are poorly understood. The deployment process includes the launching the floats from research vessels or platforms, the adjustment of the floats' positioning to ensure optimal data capture in key areas. The continuous monitoring of the floats' status through satellite communication.

Dynamic Sampling Capabilities: The floats are capable of dynamic sampling, meaning they can adjust their depth to collect data from various ocean layers. This flexibility allows researchers to monitor vertical gradients in temperature and salinity. However, for the purposes of the OCEAN: ICE project, the primary focus remains on surface-level measurements, as these are crucial for understanding sea surface temperature changes, salinity variations, and their implications for deep water formation and ocean circulation.

Data Transmission and Longevity: The training has been addressing also the floats' data transmission capabilities, particularly of interest is the issue on time: how long the floats can continue to send data after deployment. This is critical for integrating the collected data into OCEAN ICE's numerical models and simulations. The training has covered the following topics: the duration for which floats remain functional in extreme conditions (e.g., sea ice cover), the ability of floats to transmit data reliably when faced with challenges such as drifting or ice interference, how quickly can the data be transmitted once the floats resurface after a profiling cycle.

The duration of data transmission depends on several factors, including environmental conditions (sea ice, waves, temperature), float energy consumption (battery life and energy use for data transmission) and the distance of floats from relay points, such as satellites or data collection vessels. BAS has acquired very specific knowledge to this respect and has NASC with detailed documentation on the technical aspects of data transmission, including typical transmission times, expected battery life, and potential transmission challenges under different ocean conditions.

Software and Data Management: BAS has shared the software used for float data collection and analysis, along with technical guidelines for integrating float data into larger oceanographic data sets. The software

will allow NASC to monitor float performance and analyze the data in real time, ensuring smooth incorporation into OCEAN: ICE models.

Float Drift Control: BAS highlighted the importance of controlling float drift, particularly in regions with significant ice cover. Since drifting floats may provide unreliable data if they move outside designated areas, BAS has outlined how the floats' internal mechanisms can limit drift and ensure they remain within the target observation zones. This is crucial for maintaining the integrity of the data, as it will be used to improve ice sheet boundary conditions within the project's models.

Key Environmental Indicators at the Surface: The surface-level measurements are the priority for the floats. Parameters such as salinity, temperature variations, and chemical composition at the surface are critical for understanding ocean circulation, including the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). Surface processes have direct implications for deep water formation, a key factor in global ocean circulation patterns.

Adjustable Depth Sampling: While the focus is on surface-level observations, the floats' ability to adjust their sampling depth provides flexibility for future research needs. This feature allows for deeper ocean monitoring when necessary, especially in regions where vertical oceanographic processes play a significant role in environmental changes.

5. Next Steps

A more detailed planning of the upcoming cruises with the Noosphera is in the making and all the teams represented in the training sessions will regularly touch base until the start of the research cruise.

2.3 Open Science

The data to be collected by the Agro floats will be shared and commonly used by all Project partners, contributing to the open databases created earlier.

3. Results

As the results, participants of the trainings learned how to operate the Argo floats, their capacities and the expected duration of the application. This made them prepared for the own floats deployment, which is planned for March 2024.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

In perspective, the data consolidation and delivery will be achieved by making data available through the data management system of the OCEAN:ICE project. Data management will comply with FAIR principles and the OCEAN:ICE data management plan.

O8: Develop and enhance the technical skills of Ukrainian research and technical staff, strengthening competencies in deployment, analysis, dissemination, exploitation and research management.

With this training, OCEAN:ICE indirectly mobilises excellence in the Ukraine, it has contributed to improve knowledge and created new competencies and skills for working in transnational research projects.